

1. Changes in dissolved CH₄ under low C input.

2. Changes in dissolved CH₄ under high C input.

Ebullition of methane

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Up to 90% of the CH₄ released into the atmosphere from ricefields is attributed to the rice plant, but another release mechanism is ebullition as gas bubbles. Ricefields are usually prepared flooded with at least 4 wk passing before rice is transplanted. If bare mud is flooded, CH₄ is entrapped in the soil, and ebullition becomes the only major pathway for CH₄ release. Cultural practices during the

growing period enhance ebullition of soil-entrapped CH₄.

To quantify the contribution of CH₄ ebullition to total fluxes, we installed Plexiglas boxes between rice hills and measured the collected gas after 24 h throughout the growing season. We monitored CH₄ ebullition and total fluxes in plots planted to IR72 and treated with mineral fertilizers and organic amendments.

1. Variability of methane in urea plot.

Methane ebullition varied greatly in all plots (Fig. 1). The variability increased as the growing season progressed. Ebullition is higher during the day than at night and the seasonal pattern was similar to that of emission. Organic amendments increased the ebullition of CH₄ (Fig. 2).

The maximum amount of CH₄ ebullition was observed 2 wk after flooding the soil, followed by a decrease during the crop's vegetative growth. Ebullition increased again during the reproductive phase, with a final peak at harvest. Ebullition contributed 20% of the total CH₄ emission. ■

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2. Methane ebullition from ricefields. 1992 WS.

Methane production potential of soils

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Soils in which rice is grown vary from acidic to alkaline, from deficient to toxic in terms of nutrient contents, from low organic carbon (OC) to peat soils, from sand to clay, and from ones with low base status to ones with high cation exchange capacity.

We studied the effect of soil properties in CH₄ production using 20 soils from different rice-growing areas in the Philippines. Soil properties govern the electrochemical and chemical changes that occur upon flooding and the pattern of CH₄ formation. We found that soils can be grouped into four classes according to the amount of CH₄ produced during anaerobic incubation for 10 d: I < 1 μg CH₄/g soil, II < 10, III < 100, IV > 100. Each group has a distinct pattern of CH₄ formation and differs significantly in the total amount of CH₄ produced (Fig. 1), though final Eh and pH values were similar.

Soils categorized under class IV had the highest average OC (2.2%) while those in classes I and II had average OC (1.4%). Soils with >2% OC produced more than 300 μg CH₄/g. The OC

content is the only soil property that shows a significant correlation with CH₄ production. But CH₄ production and soil OC are not correlated in soils with C content of less than 2%. Sandy soils high in OC produce more CH₄ than do clay soils. With similar OC content, the negative impact of clay is probably because of the formation of organo-mineral complexes where C becomes less degradable. Clay soils may also entrap

1. Effect of soil properties Eh and pH on CH₄ production.

more CH₄, thus increasing the probability of oxidation.

Adding rice straw increased CH₄ production but did not affect the grouping of the CH₄ production potential of the soils (Fig. 2). This implies that degradable C is an important-but not the only-limiting factor for CH₄ production.

Soils that produced the highest CH₄ had low pH when air-dried. This appears to contradict the hypothesis that acidic soils produce less CH₄. The reduction of soils upon flooding converges any air-dried soil pH at about 7, which is the optimum level for CH₄ production. In acid soils, substrates that can be catabolized by methanogens may be conserved during the fallow periods and the initial reduction phase, leading to higher total CH₄ production.

The effects of soil properties on CH₄ production and oxidation are not well-understood at present. Further research is needed to elucidate the dynamic and